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Lifelong Learning in the Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022

Between 2018 and 2022 it grew on average by 22.16%

Istat calculates the value of participation in continuing education in the Italian regions. The value of participation in continuing education is defined as the percentage of people aged 25-64 who participated in education and training activities in the 4 weeks preceding the interview out of the total number of people aged 25-64. The data refers to the period 2018-2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of participation in continuous training in 2022. Trentino-Alto Adige is in first place for participation in continuous training in 2022 with a value of 14.30 units, followed by Sardinia with a value of 12, 20 units and from Emilia Romagna with an amount equal to 11.90 units. In the middle of the table are Abruzzo with an amount of 10.60 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 10.20 units, and Veneto with a value of 10.10 units. Campania and Puglia close the ranking with a value of 7.20 units up to a value of 6.30 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in participation in continuous training between 2018 and 2022. Calabria is in first place for the percentage change in participation in continuous training between 2018 and 2022 with a value of 60.38 % equal to a growth from an amount of 5.30 units up to a value of 8.50 units or equal to a value of 3.20 units. In second place is Abruzzo with a value of 55.88% equal to a growth from an amount of 6.80 units up to a value of 10.60 units or equal to an amount of 3.80 units. In third place is Lazio with a value equal to 43.90% equal to a variation from an amount of 8.20 units up to a value of 11.80 units or equal to a variation of 3.60 units.

In the middle of the ranking there is Campania with a variation equal to an amount of 26.32% equal to a variation from an amount of 5.70 units up to a value of 7.20 units or equal to an amount of 1.50 units. Then there is Liguria with a value equal to 25.27% going from an amount of 9.10 units up to a value of 11.40 units or equal to a value of 2.30 units. Finally, Sicily follows with an amount of 21.15% with a variation from 5.20 units up to a value of 6.30% or equal to an amount of 1.10 units.

Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with a variation equal to an amount of 4.42% or a variation from an amount of 11.30 units up to a value of 11.80 units or equal to a value of 0.50 units. Lombardy follows with a value of 3.30 units equal to a variation from 9.10 units up to a value of 9.40 units or a variation equal to an amount of 0.30 units. Veneto closes the ranking with a value of 3.06%, equal to a variation from an amount of 9.80 units up to a value of 10.10 units.

On average, the value of participation in continuing education in the Italian regions grows from an amount of 8.31 units up to a value of 10.15 units or equal to an amount of 1.84 units equal to a value of 22.16%.

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Participation in continuous training in the Italian macro-regions in 2018 and 2022. Participation in continuous training in Northern Italy grew from an amount of 9.6 units up to a value of 10.3 units or a variation equal to an amount of 0.70 units equal to a value of 7.29%. Participation in continuing education in the North-West grew from an amount of 8.9 units to a value of 9.6 units or a variation of 0.70 units equal to a value of 7.87%. Participation in continuous training in the North-East grew from an amount of 10.5 units up to a value of 11.3 units or equal to a variation of 0.80 units equal to a value of 7.62%. Participation in continuous training in Central Italy grew from an amount of 8.8 units up to a value of 11.2 units or equal to a variation of 2.40 units equal to an amount of 27.27%. Participation in continuous training in the South grew from an amount of 5.9 units up to a value of 7.8 units equal to an amount of 1.90 units equal to a value of 32.20%. Participation in continuous training in Southern Italy grew from an amount of 5.8 units up to a value of 7.8 units or a variation equal to an amount of 2.00 units equal to a value of 34.48%. Participation in continuous training in the Islands grew from an amount of 6 units up to a value of 7.8 units equal to a variation of 1.80 units equal to an amount of 30.00%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below is presented a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient with the identification of two clusters namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Calabria, Puglia, Campania, Sicily, Abruzzo, Basilicata, Marche, Molise;
- *Cluster 2:* Umbria, Tuscany, Liguria, Trentino-Alto Adige, Veneto, Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Sardinia, Valle d'Aosta, Lazio, Piedmont.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters, it is possible to verify the dominance of cluster 2 compared to the value of cluster 1. That is, the following ordering $C2 > C1$ occurs. The result is therefore a clear contrast between the southern regions and the central-northern regions. We can note that the only southern region belonging to the leading cluster or C2 is Sardinia.

Conclusions. The value of participation in continuing education in the Italian regions has grown on average by an amount of approximately 22.16%. However, there is still a significant gap between the regions of Southern Italy and the regions of Central-Northern Italy. In fact, the value of participation in continuing education in Southern Italy in 2022 is 24% lower than in the North and 30.3% lower than in Central Italy. The Italian population living in the regions of Southern Italy is therefore less active than the population of the Centre-North in terms of participation in continuous training. The lower value of participation in continuous training in Southern Italy compared to the value of the Center and North creates a gap in terms of human capital which prevents the Southern regions from having a prominent role in the current knowledge-oriented economic system and which could also have a deleterious effect for the development of active citizenship and the culture of institutional legality.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Partecipazione alla Formazione Continua nelle Regioni Italiane tra il 2018 ed il 2022							
Regione	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	☆ 8,40	☆ 8,80	☆ 7,00	☆ 10,40	☆ 9,40	★ 1,00	☆ 11,90
Valle d'Aosta	☆ 8,50	☆ 9,10	☆ 7,50	☆ 10,60	☆ 10,20	★ 1,70	☆ 20,00
Liguria	☆ 9,10	☆ 9,80	☆ 8,90	☆ 11,80	☆ 11,40	★ 2,30	★ 25,27
Lombardia	☆ 9,10	☆ 9,10	☆ 7,80	☆ 10,40	☆ 9,40	★ 0,30	★ 3,30
Trentino-Alto Adige	☆ 11,00	☆ 10,80	☆ 9,00	☆ 11,50	☆ 14,30	★ 3,30	★ 30,00
Veneto	☆ 9,80	☆ 9,90	☆ 7,60	☆ 10,60	☆ 10,10	★ 0,30	★ 3,06
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	☆ 11,30	☆ 11,00	☆ 8,60	☆ 12,30	☆ 11,80	★ 0,50	★ 4,42
Emilia-Romagna	☆ 11,00	☆ 10,40	☆ 9,30	☆ 12,30	☆ 11,90	★ 0,90	☆ 8,18
Toscana	☆ 10,00	☆ 9,40	☆ 8,30	☆ 11,00	☆ 10,60	★ 0,60	☆ 6,00
Umbria	☆ 9,30	☆ 10,20	☆ 8,10	☆ 11,60	☆ 11,20	★ 1,90	★ 20,43
Marche	☆ 7,90	☆ 7,70	☆ 6,20	☆ 10,10	☆ 10,00	★ 2,10	★ 26,58
Lazio	☆ 8,20	☆ 8,60	☆ 7,90	☆ 11,30	☆ 11,80	★ 3,60	★ 43,90
Abruzzo	☆ 6,80	☆ 7,20	☆ 7,00	☆ 9,30	☆ 10,60	★ 3,80	★ 55,88
Molise	☆ 7,80	☆ 7,60	☆ 7,30	☆ 9,90	☆ 10,00	★ 2,20	★ 28,21
Campania	☆ 5,70	☆ 5,30	☆ 5,20	☆ 7,20	☆ 7,20	★ 1,50	★ 26,32
Puglia	☆ 5,40	☆ 5,90	☆ 5,40	☆ 7,40	☆ 7,20	★ 1,80	★ 33,33
Basilicata	☆ 7,80	☆ 7,00	☆ 6,90	☆ 9,50	☆ 8,80	★ 1,00	☆ 12,82
Calabria	☆ 5,30	☆ 5,60	☆ 5,60	☆ 7,80	☆ 8,50	★ 3,20	★ 60,38
Sicilia	☆ 5,20	☆ 4,80	☆ 4,50	☆ 7,10	☆ 6,30	★ 1,10	★ 21,15
Sardegna	☆ 8,50	☆ 8,60	☆ 8,60	☆ 11,10	☆ 12,20	★ 3,70	★ 43,53
Media	☆ 8,31	☆ 8,34	☆ 7,34	☆ 10,16	☆ 10,15	★ 1,84	★ 22,16

Partecipazione alla Formazione Continua nelle Regioni Italiane tra il 2018 ed il 2022							
Macroregioni	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	☆ 10	☆ 10	☆ 8	☆ 11	☆ 10	★ 0,70	☆ 7,29
<i>Nord-ovest</i>	☆ 9	☆ 9	☆ 8	☆ 11	☆ 10	★ 0,70	☆ 7,87
<i>Nord-est</i>	☆ 11	☆ 10	☆ 9	☆ 12	☆ 11	★ 0,80	☆ 7,62
<i>Centro</i>	☆ 9	☆ 9	☆ 8	☆ 11	☆ 11	★ 2,40	★ 27,27
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	☆ 6	☆ 6	☆ 6	☆ 8	☆ 8	★ 1,90	★ 32,20
<i>Sud</i>	☆ 6	☆ 6	☆ 6	☆ 8	☆ 8	★ 2,00	★ 34,48
<i>Isole</i>	☆ 6	☆ 6	☆ 6	☆ 8	☆ 8	★ 1,80	★ 30,00